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Review Article

A Comprehensive Review of Phytochemical Profile and Pharmacological Attributes of *Epiphyllum Oxypetalum*

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ABSTRACT

Epiphyllum Oxypetalum belongs to the cactus family. It is a type of night blooming cereus that has various traditional therapeutic applications. The purpose of this review was to give an outline of the plant's pharmacological potential. The herb has long been used to treat several conditions such as coughs, uterine bleeding, shortness of breath, blood clots, discomfort, and bloody phlegm. This plant has few recognised pharmacological effects, including as antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-bacterial, and anti-cancer action. The plant contains a variety of chemicals including glycosides, saponins, steroids, phenols, proteins, resins, tannins, and terpenoids. The current review discusses the most recent advances in pharmacognosy, as well as the various applications of this plant in experimental investigations conducted on Epiphyllum Oxypetalum. This review will help to raise awareness of the lesser-known and less-documented aspects of Epiphyllum Oxypetalum research. With this information, new formulations can be developed or existing ones enhanced to provide more nutritional or medicinal benefits.

INTRODUCTION

The plant kingdom includes a wide variety of species, producing a diversity of bioactive molecules with different chemical scaffolds. Throughout the centuries, medicinal and aromatic plants have remained a significant part of everyday life, even with the advancements in modern medicine and the pharmaceutical industry. Moreover, plants serve as a rich and invaluable

source of natural remedies, many of which have long been utilized in traditional healing systems. However, there are numerous plant species with unexplored medicinal potential, and many others yet to be discovered. Epiphyllum Oxypetalum is a species belongs to the family Cactaceae. Epiphyllum Oxypetalum, originally found in Central America and Mexico, has a long-standing history of being used for its medicinal properties.

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It is one of the native species with a long history of useful therapeutic properties. Brahma Kamal, Nishagandhi, and night blooming cereus are some of the common names for *Epiphyllum Oxypetalum* [2]. The *Epiphyllum Oxypetalum* plant can reach a height of 2 to 6 meters and features dark green foliage. The woody, densely branched trunks and stems of these plants can reach a diameter of 2 cm or more. The leaves of these plants are lancet-shaped and low sideways. Glossy green leaves on the underside and upper surface of sharply pointed leaves, thinning, wavy and serrated leaves, narrow leaves arranged in a line with 1.6 to 1.8 mm of interest on top, nocturnal (blooming at night),

funnel-shaped and fragrant [3]. *Epiphyllum Oxypetalum* is primarily grown for ornamental purposes, but it is now also being investigated for its antibacterial and nutritional benefits [4]. This medicinal plant includes a wide range of chemicals with antioxidant and therapeutic qualities that could serve as a basis for the creation of new medications. The majority of medicinal plants contain substances called alkaloids, tannins saponins, terpenoids, flavonoids, and phenolics that are thought to have developed naturally in the plant as a means of defence against various pests and diseases [5].

Table 1: Different species of *Epiphyllum Oxypetalum*:

Sl. No	Species	Morphological Characters
1	<i>Epiphyllum Angulinger</i>	Commonly known as fishbone cactus. Mainly found in India and Mexico. profusely branched stem with nocturnal and sweet-scented flowers. Fruits are brown, green, and yellow in colour with oval shape
2	<i>Epiphyllum Oxypetalum</i>	Also known as D man's pipe and beauty under the moon. Originated from Sri Lanka, Central and North America and also in India
3	<i>Epiphyllum Crenatum</i>	derives its name due to presence of wavy-tooth i.e.-crenations in stem and is related to <i>Epiphyllum angulinger</i> . The stem is tapering which is branched. At the end forms a woody, flat, secondary stem. Linear and long leaves and has green or greyish green epidermis. Nocturnal flowers which are 18-29cm long.
4	<i>Epiphyllum Pumilum</i>	Grown as ornamental, it is native to Mexico and Guatamela. Woody based, profusely branched primary stem which form tapering ends, Secondary stem is elongated. Nocturnal, fragrant 10-15am long flowers. Sweet ovoid fruits with white pulp
5	<i>Epiphyllum Phyllanthus</i>	Called as climbing cactus, it is native to Mexico. grown as ornamental it is a species native to Mexico

Taxonomical Classification:

Table 2: Taxonomical classification of *Epiphyllum Oxypetalum*

Kingdom	Plantae
Sub-kingdom	Tracheobionta
Phylum	Magnoliophyte
Class	Magnoliopsida
Subclass	Hamamelidae
Order	Caryophyllales

Family	Cactaceae
Genus	Epiphyllum
Species	Epiphyllum Oxypetalum
Synonyms	Cereus Oxypetalum, Epiphyllum Purpusii, Phyllocactus Oxypetalus, Phyllocactus purpursii, Cactus Oxypetalus, Epiphyllum acuminatum, Phyllocactus acuminatus, Phyllocactus guyanensis, Phyllocactus grandis.

Figure 1: Plant in flowering stage and plant with leaves showing structure of *Epiphyllum Oxypetalum*

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS:

Numerous researchers have studied *Epiphyllum Oxypetalum* phytochemically, and several active chemical components have been identified upon

isolation. Chemical components such as Alkaloids, saponins, terpenoids, protein, amino acids, steroids, flavonoids, tannins [6] and triterpenoids [7] were present in the flowers. Carbohydrates, phenols, sterols, glycosides, resins [8] were present in the leaves.

Table 3: Chemical composition of *Epiphyllum Oxypetalum*

Part of Plant	Chemical composition
Flowers	Alkaloids, saponins, terpenoids, protein, amino acids, steroids, flavonoids, tannins and triterpenoids.
Leaves	Carbohydrates, proteins, tannins, phenols, Alkaloids, saponins, sterols, glycosides, resins.

Table 4: Chemical constituents of *Epiphyllum Oxypetalum*

Parts of plant	Chemical components
Flowers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hexadecenoic acid, ethyl ester Nonadecanoic acid

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Oleic acid • 11-tridecen-1-ol • 1-octadecyne • Hexadecenal • 7-hydroxy-3(1,1-dimethyl prop-2enyl) coumarin • Pterin-6-carboxylic acid
Leaves	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4-hydroxy-2-methylacetophenone • Megastigmatrienone • 4-((1E)-3-hydroxy-1-propenyl)-2 methoxyphenol • n-hexadecenoic acid • Octadecanoic acid • Phytol • Cholesta-22,24-dien-5-ol, 4,4-dimethyl • Stigmasterol • 4,22-stigmasten-3-one • Heptacosane • Nonadecane • 2- methyl- Spinasterone • 4,22-stigmastadiene-3-one • Tetracosane • Hentriacontane • Stigmast-4-en-3-one • Testosterone cypionate

Structures of some of the chemical constituents of *Epiphyllum oxypetalum*:

Nonadecanoic acid

7-hydroxy-3(1,1-dimethyl

Pterin-6-carboxylic acid

4-hydroxy-2-methyl
-acetophenone

Megastigmatrienone

Stigmasterol

2- methyl- Spinasterone

Phytochemical Analysis of flower extract:

Qualitative chemical analysis was conducted on all extracts of *Epiphyllum Oxypetalum* flowers to

identify the presence of various phytoconstituents, as detailed below:

1ml of the extract was stirred with 1ml of dil. HCl and filtered. The filtrate was tested with various reagents as follows^[9].

Table 5: Test for chemical constituents

Sl.no	Test	Inference	Observation
1	Wagner's test Extract + 2ml Wagner reagent by sides of test tube.	Reddish brown colour precipitate	Presence of alkaloids
2	Fehling's test 1ml of filtrate was boiled on a water bath + 1ml Fehling solution 1 and 2	Red precipitate	Presence of carbohydrates
3	Borntreger's test 2ml of filtrate + 3ml of chloroform. Chloroform layer was separated and 10% ammonia solution was added	Pink colour	Presence of glycosides
4	Biuret test 2ml of filtrate + 2% copper sulphate solution + 1ml of ethanol 95% to excess of potassium hydroxide pellets	Pink colour in ethanolic layer	Presence of proteins
5	Ferric chloride test 1ml of extract dissolved in 2ml of distilled water + few drops of neutral ferric chloride solution	Dark inexperienced colour	Presence of resins
6	2ml of extract + 1ml of chloroform + conc. H ₂ SO ₄	Reddish brown layer	Presence of terpenoids
7	Extract + 2ml of chloroform + few drops of acetic acid + conc. H ₂ SO ₄	Mixture of blue green colour	Presence of steroids
8	1ml of extract + 2ml of ammonia solution	Mixture of yellow colour	Presence of flavonoid
9	1ml of extract + 2 drops of ferric chloride	Green colour	Presence of tannins

Phytochemical Analysis of leaf extract:

identify the presence of various phytoconstituents, as detailed below^[10]

Qualitative chemical analysis was conducted on all extracts of *Epiphyllum Oxypetalum* leaves to

Table 6: Test for chemical constituents

Sl.no	Test	Inference	Observation
1	Molisch's test:		

	<p>1ml of extract + 2ml of alpha-naphthol + 2ml of conc.H₂SO₄ sides of the test tube</p> <p>Benedict's test: 1ml of extract + 2ml of benedict's reagent</p> <p>Barfoed's test: 2ml of leaf extract + 2mL of Barfoed's reagent. This test tube was immersed in a boiling water bath for 5 minutes</p> <p>Fehling's test: Dissolve the extract in 5ml of distilled water and filter + hydrolysis the filtrate with dil.HCL + add Fehling A and B solution</p>	<p>Purple coloured ring</p> <p>Brick red precipitate</p> <p>Brick red precipitates</p> <p>Red precipitate</p>	<p>Presence of carbohydrates</p>
2	<p>Biuret test: 3ml extract + 1ml of NaOH + 0.5ml CuSO₄ solution</p> <p>Millon's test: 2 mL extract + 1ml Millon's reagent</p> <p>Ninhydrin test: 1ml extract + 2ml Ninhydrin reagent and the test tube is heated in a boiling water bath</p>	<p>Blue colour</p> <p>Brick red colour</p> <p>violet colour</p>	<p>Presence of protein</p>
3	<p>Ferric chloride test: 2ml of the extract + 3 drops of FeCl₃ solution.</p> <p>Gelatine test: 2ml of extract + few drops of gelatine solution</p>	<p>Bluish black or greenish black colour</p> <p>Precipitation of gelatine</p>	<p>Presence of tannins</p> <p>Presence of tannins</p>
4	<p>Ferric chloride Test: 1ml of extract + 3 drops of FeCl₃ solution</p>	<p>Bluish black precipitate</p>	<p>presence of phenols.</p>
5	<p>Wagner's test: 1ml of the extract + 3 drops of Wagner's Reagent</p> <p>Mayer's test: 1ml of the extract + 3 drops of Mayer's reagent</p>	<p>brownish black colour</p> <p>white colour</p>	<p>presence of alkaloid.</p> <p>presence of alkaloid.</p>

	Dragendorff's Test: 1ml of the extract + 3 drops of Dragendorff's reagent	brownish red colour	
6	Ferric chloride test: 2ml of the extract + 0.5ml of FeCl ₃ solution. Alkaline reagent test: 5 drops of dilute NaOH + 2ml of the extract.	Intense green colour yellow colour which changes to colourless on addition of dilute HCl	Presence of flavonoids
7	Liebermann Burchard's Test: 2 mL of the extract + 2 mL of chloroform + 2 mL of glacial acetic acid + 2ml of concentrated H ₂ SO ₄ is added along the sides of the test tube Salkowski test: 1ml of the extract + 1 mL of chloroform + 1 mL conc. H ₂ SO ₄ is added along the side of the test tube	green colour in the chloroform layer Reddish colour	presence of sterols.

Pharmacology:

Epiphyllum Oxypetalum plant species has shown various activities as that in picture:

Figure 2: Pharmacological activity of *Epiphyllum Oxypetalum*

Anti-Inflammatory Activity:

Infectious microorganisms like bacteria, viruses, or fungi typically cause inflammation when they enter the body, settle in certain tissues, or move through the bloodstream. Additionally, events including tissue damage, cell death, malignancy, ischaemia, and degeneration can all cause inflammation. During various forms of inflammatory responses, a large number of inflammatory mediators are produced and released. Pro and anti-inflammatory mediators are the two primary categories into which inflammatory chemicals are typically separated [11].

The fresh plant of *Epiphyllum Oxypetalum* was collected and authenticated, then the fresh leaves were shed dried and coarsely powdered in a mechanical grinder. Successive, extraction was carried out using ethanol and water in Soxhlet apparatus. After complete solvent removal, the

extract weighed and stored in a desiccator until further use. The Anti-inflammatory activity of *Epiphyllum Oxypetalum* ethanolic extract was evaluated on rats. Both sexes of adult Albino Wistar rats weighing 150–200g were chosen. The rats were given a week to get used to the lab environment before the treatment. The animals were kept in polypropylene cages with a maximum of four animals per cage under conventional laboratory settings, which included a temperature of $25^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$, a relative humidity of $50 \pm 5\%$, and a photoperiod of 10 hours dark and 14 hours light. The use of animals in the experiments was approved by the institutional animal ethics committee. The department of animal ethics committee accepted the study's protocol, and the procedures were conducted in accordance with CPCSEA criteria.

Experimental design:

The study was carried out by using six groups of six animals

Group 1	Control group	Normal saline (0.5% sodium CMC solution)
Group 2	Test group	200 mg/kg of alcohol extract
Group 3	Test group	400 mg/kg of alcohol extract
Group 4	Test group	600 mg/kg of alcohol extract
Group 5	Test group	200 mg/kg of aqueous extract
Group 6	Test group	400 mg/kg of aqueous extract
Group 7	Test group	600 mg/kg of aqueous extract
Group 8	Standard drug	Aspirin 10 mg/kg

At different time intervals (0, 1, 2, 3 and 5 hours), the plethysmometer was used to measure the change in the inflammatory reaction and compare it to the control group. Inhibition of right hind paw oedema at various test and standard medication dosages was determined using the following formula.

$$\text{percentage of paw oedema inhibition} = \frac{(\text{Vt}-\text{Vo})}{\text{control} - (\text{Vt}-\text{Vo}) \text{ treated}} \times 100$$

(Vt-Vo) control

where Vt is the rat paw volume at time "t"

- Vo is the rat paw volume at the beginning (prior to carrageenan injection)
- (Vt-Vo) control is the oedema generated in the control group, and

- (Vt-Vo) treated is the oedema generated during treatment.
- Preparation of human Red Blood Cells (HRBC) suspension

In-vitro evaluation of anti-inflammatory activity:

- Heat induced haemolytic activity

2) Inhibition of albumin denaturation

1) Membrane stabilisation method

Table 7: In vitro evaluation of anti-inflammatory activity of alcohol and aqueous extract of *Epiphyllum Oxypetalum* leaves

Dose	Inhibition of Protein denaturation (% inhibition ± SEM)		Membrane stabilization (% inhibition ± SEM)	
	Alcohol extract	Aqueous extract	Alcohol extract	Aqueous extract
100 µg/ml	23.93±1.12	36.38±0.99	23.45±1.72	34.89±0.91
200 µg/ml	30.81±0.92	45.45±1.80	33.47±1.45	45.73±0.59
300 µg/ml	39.45±1.51	55.70±1.03	41.12±0.74	54.30±0.98
Standard drug 100 µg/ml	72.10±1.78		77.5±1.02	

In the inhibition of protein denaturation, the maximum inhibition 39.45% and 55.70% was seen at concentration 300µg/ml in alcohol and aqueous extract respectively. Aspirin, standard anti-inflammatory drug showed maximum inhibition 72.10% at concentration 100µg/ml. In Membrane stabilization, the maximum inhibition 41.12% and 54.30% was seen at concentration 300µg/ml in alcohol and aqueous extract respectively. The aspirin, standard drug showed the maximum inhibition 77.5% at 100µg/ml. Therefore, it was concluded that the aqueous extract of *Epiphyllum Oxypetalum* showed more anti-inflammatory activity than alcohol extract [12].

Anti-Oxidant Activity:

The radical scavengers which protect the human body against free radical that causes pathological condition is known as anti-oxidants. The present concept of toxicity is due to the participation of oxygen free radicals or reactive oxygen species. Therefore, it becomes essential to test the antioxidant potential of the plant material [13].

Natural anti-oxidants or phytochemical anti-oxidants are the secondary metabolites of plants [14]. Some of the antioxidants produced by the plants include carotenoids, flavonoids, tocopherols, Beta carotene, Lycopene, Sesamol, Anthocyanins, Catechins, Ellagic acid, Lutein, Resveratrol, cinnamic acids, benzoic acids, folic acid, ascorbic acid, tocotrienols etc.,[15]. The *Epiphyllum Oxypetalum* belongs to the cactaceae family have much attention towards the development of the ethno medicines with strong anti-oxidant properties. The fresh plant of *Epiphyllum Oxypetalum* was collected and authenticated, then the fresh leaves were shed dried and coarsely powdered in a mechanical grinder. Successive, extraction was carried out using ethanol in Soxhlet apparatus at 40-50°C. the extraction process is carried out at 80°C.

The Anti-inflammatory activity of *Epiphyllum Oxypetalum* ethanolic extract was evaluated by using two methods:

1) DPPH (1, 1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl) radical scavenging assay method

(100–2000 µg/ml) or a standard solution of 10–100 µg/ml. After 30 minutes, absorbance was measured at 517 nm.

2) Hydrogen peroxide scavenging assay method

1) DPPH (1, 1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl) radical scavenging assay method:

A stable radical called DPPH was used to test the hydrogen-donating or radical-scavenging capabilities of alcohol and aqueous extracts as well as the standard vitamin C, L-ascorbic acid. A 0.1 mM DPPH solution in alcohol was made, shielded from light by keeping it dark, and folded with aluminium foil. 3ml of this solution were then added to 1ml of extracts at different concentrations

The percentage inhibition activity was calculated using the following formula:

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = [(A \text{ control} - A \text{ test})/A \text{ control}] \times 100$$

Were,

- A control- Absorbance of the control
- A test - Absorbance of extract/standard taken as ascorbic acid

Assay:

Table 8: DPPH scavenging activity of alcohol extract and aqueous extract of leaves Absorbance of control = 0.59±0.007

Sl.no	Concentration in µg/ml	Alcohol extract		Aqueous extract	
		Absorbance at 517nm	% inhibition ± SD	Absorbance at 517nm	% inhibition ± SD
1	100	0.481±0.008	18.47±0.76	0.531±0.01	9.77±1.67
2	200	0.421±0.004	28.74±0.89	0.524±0.004	11.51±1.19
3	300	0.362±0.007	38.73±1.73	0.492±0.005	16.65±1.23
4	400	0.315±0.005	46.58±0.88	0.476±0.004	19.41±0.75
5	2000	0.234±0.007	60.37±1.67	0.388±0.002	34.23±0.88

Table 9: DPPH scavenging activity of standard drug ascorbic acid

Sl.no	Concentration in µg/ml	Absorbance at 517nm	% inhibition ± SD
1	10	0.055±0.002	90.63±0.51
2	20	0.054±0.0008	90.91±0.1
3	30	30 0.050±0.001	91.48±0.19
4	50	50 0.045±0.002	92.33±0.33
5	80	80 0.028±0.002	95.26±0.43

Figure 3: Graphical representation of DPPH radical scavenging assay of alcohol and aqueous drug

Figure 4: Graphical representation of DPPH radical scavenging assay of standard drug ascorbic acid

It was found that the radical-scavenging activities of all the extracts increased with increasing concentration. Maximum inhibition by alcohol extract (60.37 ± 1.67) and aqueous extract (34.23 ± 0.88) was shown at $2000 \mu\text{g/ml}$ concentration whereas ascorbic acid showed maximum inhibition (95.26 ± 0.43) at $80 \mu\text{g/ml}$ concentration.

2) Hydrogen peroxide scavenging assay method:

This assay method was used to determine the extract's capacity to scavenge hydrogen peroxide. 4ml of extract was prepared using distilled water

at different concentrations ($100 \mu\text{g}$ to $500 \mu\text{g}$). The extracts were then combined with 0.6 millilitres of a 4 mM H_2O_2 solution made in phosphate buffer (0.1 M with pH 7.4) and incubated for ten minutes. The absorbance was measured at 230 nm against a blank solution that contained the plant extract without H_2O_2 . Ascorbic acid was used as a standard reference.

The percentage inhibition activity was calculated using the following formula –

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \frac{[(A \text{ control} - A \text{ test}) / A \text{ control}] \times 100}{}$$

Were, A control- Absorbance of the control Assay:

A test - Absorbance of extract/standard taken as ascorbic acid

Table 10: Hydrogen Peroxide scavenging assay of alcohol extract and aqueous extract of leaves
Absorbance of control = 0.59±0.007

Sl.no	Concentration in µg/ml	Alcohol extract Absorbance at 230nm	% inhibition ± SD	Aqueous extract Absorbance at 230nm	% inhibition ± SD
1	100	0.617±0.02	15.92±0.72	0.653±0.02	11.03±0.25
2	200	0.534±0.02	27.25±1.04	0.622±0.02	15.24±0.65
3	300	0.500±0.01	31.8±1.15	0.594±0.01	18.93±1.43
4	400	0.442±0.02	39.78±1.83	0.567±0.01	22.72±1.16
5	500	0.412±0.009	43.76±0.97	0.521±0.01	27.07±0.16

Table 11: Hydrogen Peroxide scavenging assay of standard drug ascorbic acid

Sl.no	Concentration in µg/ml	Absorbance at 230nm	% inhibition ± SD
1	100	0.131±0.003	82.03±1.83
2	200	0.122± 0.005	83.34±2.04
3	300	0.107±0.007	85.37±2.33
4	400	0.094±0.006	87.11±2.09
5	500	0.068±0.003	90.64±1.15

Figure 5: Graphical representation of hydrogen peroxide scavenging assay of alcohol and aqueous extract of *Epiphyllum Oxypetalum* leaves

Figure 6: Graphical representation of hydrogen peroxide scavenging assay of standard drug ascorbic acid

The Maximum inhibition by alcohol extract (43.76 ± 0.97) and aqueous extract (27.07 ± 0.16) was shown at $500 \mu\text{g/ml}$ concentration whereas ascorbic acid showed maximum inhibition (90.64 ± 1.15) at $100 \mu\text{g/ml}$ concentration. The antioxidant activity tested by DPPH radical scavenging assay and Hydrogen peroxide scavenging assay was found to be positive for both the extracts which can be attributed to the presence of phenols and flavonoids. The higher antioxidant activity was shown by alcohol extract. The alcohol extract and aqueous extract exhibited antioxidant activity. The maximum antioxidant activity was shown by the alcohol extract than the aqueous extract. Thus, it can be concluded that the *Epiphyllum Oxypetalum* exhibits antioxidant activity^[15].

ANTI-UROLITHIATIC ACTIVITY:

Urolithiasis is derived from the Greek words ouron (urine) and lithos (stone). Urolithiasis refers to the accretion of hard, solid and non-metallic minerals in the urinary tract. A hard, crystalline mineral substance that forms in the kidney or urinary tract is called a kidney stone. Renal calculi are another name for kidney stones. Nephrolithiasis is the name for kidney stone disease^[16]. Around 12% of the world population is affected by the urolithiasis. The physiochemical process of

calcified kidney stone production involves crystal nucleation, aggregation, and growth, and it is facilitated by a number of biological events, including increased calcium or sodium oxalate, urates, urine volume, and pH. According to their size, type, and location, 90% of patients with upper urinary tract stones are currently treated, with success rates ranging from 68 to 86%. Approximately 75% of all renal stones are caused by calcium phosphate or calcium oxalate, and eating more protein has been associated with an increased risk of developing renal stones^[17]. The *Epiphyllum Oxypetalum* leaves was collected and authenticated. The leaves were cleaned with water, dried and grind into a fine powder using blender. Extracted with ethanol using Soxhlet extractor for 6 to 8 hours. Filter the extract using a muslin cloth, transfer it to 50 ml tubes and centrifuge it for 15 minutes at 25°C at 4,000 rpm.

Investigation of anti-urolithiatic activity test by *in-vitro* using a titration method:

In the laboratory, calcium oxalate kidney stones were produced by mixing an equimolar solution of sodium oxalate in 10 ml of 2N H_2SO_4 with dehydration of calcium chloride in distilled water. Both processes were given enough distilled water to react in a beaker, producing calcium oxalate precipitate. An ammonia solution is used to remove any last traces of sulfuric acid from the

precipitate, which is then rinsed with distilled water and dried at 60°C. 1 gm of calcium oxalate and 10 gm of extract were combined in an egg's semi-permeable membrane to measure the calcium oxalate dissolving percentage. This was suspended with 100 cc of 0.1M Tris buffer in a conical flask. The first group only had 1 mg of calcium oxalate, serving as a control. As a positive check, the second group had 10 mg of Cystone and 1 mg of calcium oxalate. Both the third and fourth groups have one milligram of calcium oxalate and ethanol extracts. All group's conical flasks were heated to 37°C for two hours in incubator. The contents of the semi-permeable membranes for each group should be placed in different test tubes. 2 ml of 1N sulfuric acid is added to each test tube with acid after titrating with 0.9494 N KMnO₄ until the end point is achieved and the colour turns deep pink. To determine the total amount of various solvent

extracts of dissolved calcium oxalate, subtract the amount of calcium oxalate that was still present after the experiment's first run.

Table 12: % calcium oxalate (CaOx) dissolution by *Epiphyllum Oxypetalum* leaves extracts

Sl.no	Groups	<i>Epiphyllum Oxypetalum</i>
1	Blank	0%
2	Positive management	73%
3	Extract of ethanol	80%

This study evaluates the effectiveness of ethanolic extract of *Epiphyllum Oxypetalum* on anti-urolithiatic activity. The maximum rate of calcium oxalate "CaOx" dissolution, 80% was seen in the ethanolic extract. It was shown that ethanolic extracts of *Epiphyllum Oxypetalum* were more effective at dissolving calcium oxalate.

Figure 7: Urolithiasis percentage of ethanolic extract of *Epiphyllum Oxypetalum* according to their concentration

From this study an in-vitro anti-urolithiatic model was used in the study to calculate the kidney stone's disintegration percentage. The solubility of the ethanol leaf extract from *Epiphyllum Oxypetalum* is higher than that of the reference drug Cystone [18].

ANTHELMINTIC ACTIVITY:

Helminths is a Greek word meaning "worm". Helminth infection is common parasitic infection affecting large number of populations, especially children. Helminths could be classified into three classes as Nematodea, Cestoidea and Trematodea. A wide range of worms are observed varying size from less than 1mm -1m. People living in Australia, south-east Asia, India, Mexico, Sri Lanka, and Thailand are most affected by this

infection. Helminths mainly enter through the contaminated drinking water or raw meats from infected animals. They may also enter into the body through skin by insect bites or walking and swimming in the contaminated soil and water. Helminths require a living host for survival, reproduction causing physical, nutritional, cognitive impairment in young children. Anthelmintic drugs are drugs which are used for treatment of helminthic infections caused by various worms. These are the drugs which act locally to emit the worms from GIT or may also act systematically to eliminate adult helminths and prevent tissue and organs from developmental forms^[19]. The *Epiphyllum Oxypetalum* leaves were collected and authenticated. The leaves were cleaned with the fresh water and dried in the shade. The dried leaves were grinded into fine powder using blender. The powder was extracted with the ethanol using Soxhlet extraction process. After extraction the extract is filtered using muslin cloth and transferred it to 50ml tubes and centrifuged for 15mins at 4000rpm at 25 °C. Finally, the extract is analysed for photochemical constituents.

Assessment of *In-vitro* Anthelmintic Activity of *Epiphyllum Oxypetalum*:

Pheritima Posthuma, an adult Indian earthworm, was treated with anthelmintics. The standard medication albendazole was diluted with sterile saline and then added to Petri plates concentrations of 25, 50, and 100 milligrams per millilitre. Ethanolic extracts from leaves were mixed with ordinary saline to create concentrations of 25, 50, and 100 mg/ml. The saline solution served as the negative control. Consequently, the Petri plates were filled with each of these dilutions. For the experiment, earthworms were split up into six groups (n = 6). In every Petri dish, earthworms of roughly the same size were kept at the same temperature. The point at which there was no movement of any kind other than when the worms were severely disoriented is used to calculate the duration of impairment. Once it was determined that the worms did not move when severely shaken or when submerged in warm water at 50°C, the moment of death for each individual worm was recorded. Minutes were used to express both the paralysis and death times.

Table 13: Results of *In-vitro* Anthelmintic activity of *Epiphyllum Oxypetalum*

Name of drug	Concentrations	Paralysis time(min)	Death time(min)
Albendazole	25mg/ml	30min 9sec	40min 11sec
	50mg/ml	19min 40sec	24min 35sec
	100mg/ml	17min 37sec	20min 10sec
Ethanolic extract	25mg/ml	24min 32sec	21min 36sec
	50mg/ml	15min 23sec	17min 25sec
	100mg/ml	11min 23sec	12min 25sec

According to this study, the *Epiphyllum Oxypetalum* had varied degree of anthelmintic activity. The ethanolic extract of *Epiphyllum Oxypetalum* showed anthelmintic activity, and the plant extract may be a significant source of anthelmintic to treat helminthic disease^[20].

REFERENCES

- Ghorbanpour M, Hadian J, Nikabadi S, Varma A. Importance of medicinal and aromatic plants in human life. Medicinal plants and environmental challenges. 2017:1-23.
- Biswal RA, Jayashree P, Mirunaalini K, Pazhamalai V. Molecular docking studies of bioactive compounds from the leaves of *Epiphyllum Oxypetalum* against *Treponema*

- pallidum, Zika virus and liver cirrhosis. *Journal of Applied Pharmaceutical Science*. 2019;4;9(11):069-77.
3. Mahmud A, Shaharun MS, Saad B, Dash GK. Epiphyllum Oxypetalum Haw.: A lesser-known medicinal plant. *Indo American Journal of pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2017;1;4(10): 3670-3672.
 4. Jeelani SM, Rather GA, Sharma A, Lattoo SK. In perspective: Potential medicinal plant resources of Kashmir Himalayas, their domestication and cultivation for commercial exploitation. *Journal of applied research on medicinal and aromatic plants*. 2018;1; 8:10-25.
 5. Prajitha P, Suresh A, Deepak VS, Faslu H. A review on Epiphyllum Oxypetalum (DC) Haw. *Asian Journal of Research in Chemistry and Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2019;7(3):824-830.
 6. Patel A, Patel S, Sanke P, Potlakayala S, Rudrabhatla S. Medicinally Important Compounds in the Flowers of Three Higher Plants: Cannabis, Saffron, and Epiphyllum Oxypetalum. *Biomedical Journal of Scientific & Technical Research*. 2021;36(5):28996-9001
 7. Artini NP, Aryasa IW. Aktivitas Antioksidan Ekstrak Bunga Wijaya Kusuma (Epiphyllum Oxypetalum). *Jurnal Ilmiah Medicamento*. 2018;29;4(2).
 8. Lesmana CA, Hikmawanti NP, Yumita A. Pharmacognosy, phytochemical, and pharmacology of wijaya kusuma (Epiphyllum Oxypetalum (DC.) Haw.)—An update review. *Borneo Journal of Pharmacy*. 2022;31;5(2):115-125.
 9. Jayashree P, Shalini M, Meenambiga SS, Suganya V. Phytochemical Screening and GC-MS Analysis of Epiphyllum Oxypetalum flower extracts. *Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology*. 2020;13(12):5893-5897.
 10. Devi KS, Narayana SL, Menghani P, Georgekutty J. Microscopic, pharmacognostic and phytochemical screening of Epiphyllum Oxypetalum (dc) haw leaves. *J Pharmacogn Phytochem*. 2018;7(6):972-980.
 11. Azab A, Nassar A, Azab AN. Anti-inflammatory activity of natural products. *Molecules*. 2016;1;21(10):1321.
 12. Rucha Dandekar RD, Bharti Fegade BF, Arvind Naik AN. Evaluation of anti-inflammatory activity of alcohol and aqueous extract of Epiphyllum Oxypetalum leaves 2015; 4(7):851-858.
 13. Umadevi U and Kamalam M, Screening of an indigenous medicinal plant – Madhuca longifolia for its antioxidant and antimicrobial properties, *Int. J. Pharm. Sci. Res.*, 2015;6(1): 273-276.
 14. Walton NJ, Brown DE, Harborne JB, Michael AJ, Parr AJ, Van Beek TA, Massiot G, Lavaud C, Nuzillard JM, Simmonds MS, Grayer RJ, editors. *Chemicals from plants: perspectives on plant secondary products*. World Scientific; 1999;26.
 15. Dandekar R, Fegade B, Bhaskar VH. In vitro evaluation of free radical scavenging activities of Epiphyllum Oxypetalum. *World J Pharm Res*. 2015;27;4(7):1301-1309.
 16. Srinivas S, Venkanna B, Madan Mohan E, Krishna-Mohan C. Urolithiasis: overview. *Int J Pharm Res Biomed Anal*. 2012;1(1):20-31.
 17. Mikawlawng K., Kumar S., Vandana R. Current scenario of urolithiasis and the use of medicinal plants as antiurolithiatic agents in Manipur (North East India): a review. *International Journal of Herbal Medicine*. 2014;0(1):1-12.
 18. Pore AV, Bais SK, Kazi SM, Nikte AA. Assessment of in-anti urolithiatic activity Epiphyllum Oxypetalum. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Herbal Technology*. 2023;1(2):72-6.

19. Omkar A.D, Sachin A.M. Assessment of Anthelmintic activity of Pisum Sativum. *Int. J. Pharm. Sci. Res.*, 2022;76(1):7-12.
20. Pore AV, Bais SK, Kazi SM, Dhumal SS. Assessment of in Vitro Anthelmintic Activity of Epiphyllum Oxypetalum. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Herbal Technology*. 2023;1(2):77-80.

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